

**LEARNING STYLE OF STUDENTS BELONGING TO PRIVATE AND
GOVERNMENT SCHOOLS**

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Abstract:

Educating each individual in the classroom through individualized instruction is not a dream nowadays. To meet with the challenges which arise due to the fact that individuals differ very much in all aspects of their personality, various methods and techniques have been developed by researchers, educationists and psychologist. Identifying student's learning style is one of the method which may be used for individualized instruction. Objective of the present research is to study the learning style of students belonging to Govt. and private schools. Sampling of 296 private school students and 291 Govt. school students has been taken for the present study. Learning Style Inventory by Dr. S.C. Agarwal has been used for collection of data. Learning style which are considered in this inventory are- Individualistic vs. non-individualistic, Field independent vs. field dependent, Motivation centered vs. motivation non-centered, Modality preference (Aural vs. visual), Environment oriented vs. environment free, Flexible vs. non-flexible, Short attention span vs. long attention span. The reliability coefficient ranged from 0.841 to 0.912. Chi square has been used to analyse the data and it is found that the students belonging to government schools and private schools do not differ significantly on learning style Individualistic vs. Non-individualistic and Environment oriented vs. Environment free. The students belonging to private schools have shown preference for Flexible learning style, Visual learning style, Field-independent learning style, Short attention span learning style, Motivation-centered learning style in comparison to government school students.

Key words : *Learning style, Government school, Private school*

Introduction

Educating each individual in the classroom through individualized instruction is not a dream nowadays. To meet with the challenges which arise due to the fact that individuals differ very much in all aspects of their personality,

various methods and techniques have been developed by researchers, educationists and psychologist. Identifying student's learning style is one of the methods which may be used for individualized instruction.

The style is most pervasive phenomenon of the contemporary society. Different writers have used this term in a variety of contexts, viz. in high street fashions, the 'sports arena', the arts, the media and many academic disciplines including educational psychology. This term may be observed to describe the grace of a gymnast, or the game of a football team, the manner and cut of new fashion on the modeling catwalk, the approach used by a commercial company to organize itself, or even the way a person may think, learn, talk or teach (Rayner and Riding, 1977). However, in the field of psychology, it has been developed in a number of different areas for example, personality, cognition, communication, motivation, perception, learning, teaching, behavior, leadership, management and decision making etc.

Thus the concept of style has been invariably used to describe an individual's quality, form, activity, or behavior sustained over time and has been nevertheless associated with individuality. It represents a distinct notion of coherent singularity in a variety of contexts and has a wide appeal to human life.

Definitions of learning styles are as varied as the individual's dealing with the concept. However, it may be concluded that learning style is a unique way of an individual learner with which he/she prefers to approach the learning task.

The Learning Style Inventory of Dr. Subhash Chandra Agarwal has been used for the present study. There are total seven types of learning style which are considered in this inventory. They are given below:

1. Individualistic vs. non-individualistic
2. Field independent vs. field dependent
3. Motivation centered vs. motivation non-centered
4. Modality preference (Aural vs. visual)

5. Environment oriented vs. environment free
6. Flexible vs. non-flexible
7. Short attention span vs. long attention span

Objective

Objective of the present research is to study the learning style of students belonging to private and government schools.

Hypothesis

There is no significant difference in the learning styles of students belonging to private and government schools.

Sampling

Sampling of 296 private school students and 291 Govt. school students has been taken for the present study using random sampling technique from Gangapur City block of SawaiMadhopur district in Rajasthan.

Tool Used

Learning Style Inventory by Dr. S.C.Agarwal has been used for the present study. The reliability has been established by test-retest method. The reliability coefficient ranged from 0.841 to 0.912. As the coefficients are quite satisfactory, the inventory is suitable for measuring students learning styles.

Statistical Calculation

The obtained raw scores have been tabulated and chi-square have been calculated in the following tables

Table 1 Comparison of learning style-1 of students belonging to private school and govt. school

Learning Style → School ↓	Flexible	Non-flexible	Total	Chi-square value
<i>private school</i>	<i>173</i>	<i>123</i>	<i>296</i>	<i>13.47</i> <i>p ≤ .001</i>
<i>Govt. school</i>	<i>126</i>	<i>165</i>	<i>291</i>	
<i>Total</i>	<i>299</i>	<i>288</i>	<i>587</i>	

It is apparent from table 1 that the Chi-square value for learning style -1 for the students belonging to private school and Govt. school has come out to be 13.47 which is significant at .001 level of significance. It indicates that both the groups of students significantly differ with regard to Flexible vs. Non-flexible learning style. Thus sub hypothesis Ho1.2 is rejected. Further the table value indicates flexible learning style is peculiar to students belonging to private school and Non-flexible learning style distinctly peculiar to students belonging to Govt. school.

Table 2 Comparison of learning style-2 of students belonging to private school and govt. school

Learnin g Style → School ↓	Indi vidualistic	Non- individualist ic	T otal	C hi- square value
private school	159	137	296	1.63 NS
Govt. school	141	150	291	
Total	300	287	587	

As the table 2 indicates, the Chi-square value for the learning style -2 i.e. Individualistic vs. Non-individualistic has come out to be 1.63, which is not significant. It leads to conclusion that the students belonging to private school and Govt. school do not differ significantly with regard to Individualistic vs. Non-individualistic learning style. Hence null hypothesis is accepted. Further it can be concluded that students belonging to private school and Govt. school have almost similar preferences to learning style Individualistic vs. Non-individualistic.

Table 3 Comparison of learning style-3 of students belonging to private school and govt. school

learning style → School ↓	Visual	Aural	Total	Chi-square value
private school	167	129	296	11.19 P ≤ .001
Govt. school	124	167	291	
Total	291	296	587	

It is apparent from table 3 that the Chi-square value for learning style -3 for the students belonging to private school and Govt. school has come out to be 11.19 which is significant at .001 level of significance. It indicates that both the groups of students significantly differ with regard to Visual vs. Aural learning style. Thus null hypothesis is rejected. Further the table value indicates Visual learning style is peculiar to students belonging to private school and Aural learning style distinctly peculiar to students belonging to Govt. school.

Table 4 Comparison of learning style-4 of students belonging to private school and govt. school

learning style → School ↓	Field independent	Field dependent	Total	Chi-square value
private school	160	136	296	6.79 p ≤ .01
Govt. school	126	165	291	
Total	286	301	587	

It is clear from table 4 that the Chi-square value for learning style -4 for the students belonging to private school and Govt. school has come out to be 6.79 which is significant at .01 level of significance. It indicates that both the group of students significantly differs with regard to Field independent vs. Field dependent learning style. Thus null hypothesis is rejected. Further the table value indicates

Field independent learning style is peculiar to students belonging to private school and Field dependent learning style distinctly peculiar to students belonging to Govt. school.

Table 5 Comparison of learning style-5 of students belonging to private school and govt. school

learning style → School ↓	Short Attention-span	Long Attention-span	Total	Chi-square value
private school	157	139	296	3.16 p≤.10
Govt. school	133	158	291	
Total	290	297	587	

It is apparent from table 5 that the Chi-square value for learning style -5 for the students belonging to schools affiliated to private school and Govt. school has come out to be 3.16 which is significant at .10 level of significance. It indicates that both the groups of students significantly differ with regard to Short attention-span vs. Long attention-span learning style. Thus null hypothesis rejected. Further the table value indicates Short attention-span learning style is peculiar to students belonging to private school and Long attention-span learning style distinctly peculiar to students belonging to Govt. school.

Table 6 Comparison of learning style-6 of students belonging to private school and govt. school

Learning Style → Board ↓	Motivation Centered	Motivation Non-centered	Total	Chi-square value
private school	162	134	296	5.105 p≤.05
Govt. school	132	159	291	
Total	294	293	587	

It is apparent from table 6 that the Chi-square value for learning style -6 for the students belonging to private school and Govt. school has come out to be 5.15 which is significant at .05 level of significance. It indicates that both the groups of students significantly differ with regard to Motivation centered vs. Motivation non-centered learning style. Thus null hypothesis is rejected. Further the table value indicates Motivation centered learning style is peculiar to students belonging to private school and Motivation non-centered learning style distinctly peculiar to students belonging to Govt. school.

Table 7 Comparison of learning style-7 of students belonging to private school and govt. school

Learnin g Style → Board ↓	Environment Oriented	Environment Free	T otal	Chi -square val ue
private school	158	138	296	2.33 NS
Govt. school	137	154	291	
Total	295	292	587	

It is evident from table 7 that the Chi-square value for the learning style -7 i.e. Environment Oriented vs. Environment Free has come out to be 2.33, which is not significant. It leads to conclusion that the students belonging to private school and Govt. school do not differ with regard to Environment Oriented vs. Environment Free learning style. Therefore null hypothesis is accepted. Further it can be concluded that students belonging to private school and Govt. school have almost similar preferences to learning style-7.

Discussion

The students belonging to private school possess flexible learning style as compared to the students belonging to Govt. schools.

The above findings indicate that students of private schools do not depend only upon the class room studies but they use variety of channels of learning They have inclination for experimentation, discussion and involvement in the acquisition of knowledge and skills in their subjects. The situation is quite different in case of Govt. school where the school environment is suffered to be rigid, overcrowded and non-conducive, which may be responsible for their preferences for non-flexible learning style.

The students belonging to both types of schools do not differ significantly in their preferences for individualistic vs. non- individualistic learning style.

It seems obvious as there are some students who can work individually without the assistance by the other, on the other hand some like to work in a group or in a team. This is the personal nature of the students which seem to be affected by some factors other than school environment.

The students belonging to private school possess visual learning style as compared to the students belonging to Govt. schools who prefer aural.

The above conclusion indicates that private school and Govt. school varies in developing visual or aural learning style. It may be due to the reason that in Govt. school teachers do not use teaching aids. More emphasis is seems on lecturing while teaching. Students depend fully on their teacher's lectures .This results in the development of aural learning style among them. On the other hand, the teachers in private schools use visual material aids while teaching. This helps in developing and sharpening visual learning style among the students in private schools.

The students belonging to private school preferred field-independent learning style, while that of belonging to Govt. school possess field-dependent learning style.

It may be taken to explain that students from different schools have shown differential preferences on this learning style which seems very indisputableprivate

school and Govt. school, the prevailing environment in these schools happens to be different from each other. Govt. school suffers with rigid and controlled environment, private schools provide quite flexible, unstructured and dynamic environment which further develops divergent thinking in the students and results in developing field-independent learning style.

The students belonging to private school have been found possessing short attention span learning style in comparison to the students of Govt. school who exhibited their preference for long attention span learning style.

The above findings indicates that students in Govt. schools are required to sit for a longer duration to perform same type of task; they do not receive variety of tasks to accomplish. In private school the total environment seems to be such in which there may be varied learning tasks and they may be structured in a way which requires short attention span learning style on the parts of its students.

The students from private school have been found having motivation centered learning style in comparison to their counterparts in Govt. school having motivation non-centered learning style.

The above findings indicate that students in Govt. schools do not get proper motivation for their work in comparison to the students studying in private school. The students in these schools are appreciated for their success. Teachers and parents are result oriented so they motivate their children in many ways. In contrast to this in Govt. schools the teachers and parents do not take interest in the success of their students which in turn develops a feeling of indifference in the children with regard to their academic achievement.

No significant difference has been found among the students of private school and Govt. school with reference to their preference for environment oriented and environment free learning style.

This may be due to the reason that though the students in both the institutions come from different level families but they require less or more same

learning situations. So the schools do not seem to play considerable role in developing student's preference for environment oriented and environment free learning style.

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